

Predicting the Final Points of the Decathlon Based on the Results of the First Day Events using Regression Analysis

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Abstract:

The decathlon is a complex athletics discipline that combines ten track and field events held over the course of two days for male athletes. These ten events can be classified as "running," "jumping," and "throwing" events. A dataset was gathered from the competition results of all Olympic games and world athletics championships between 1984 and 2023 ($n = 595$), and it was divided into training (90%) and testing (10%) subsets.

The main objective of this study is to predict the decathlon final points using the five events of the first day. The training and test sets were resampled 10,000 times from the original dataset. Then, four regression models were applied to test which model fits the data better, and the root mean square error (RMSE) was used as a model performance criterion. The results showed that the final performance is highly influenced by long jump (LJ), which is one of the first day events. In addition, the multiple linear regression model, partial least squares regression model, and quantile regression model were the best performing models to predict the final results, but the multiple linear regression model is recommended because of its simplicity.

Keywords: decathlon, multiple linear regression model, partial least square regression, quantile regression, principal component regression model, root mean square error (RMSE).

1. Introduction

The decathlon is a complex athletics discipline that combines ten track and field events held over two days for male athletes. The ten events in the decathlon were chosen to represent a broad spectrum of athletic skills, encompassing sprinting (100 m, 400 m, 110 m hurdles, and 1500 m), jumping (long jump, high jump, and pole vault), and throwing (shot put, discus throw, and javelin throw).

Several studies explored decathlon data using multivariate analysis, such as principal component analysis, factor analysis, and cluster analysis. One of the earliest works was in 1962 when Zatsiorsky and Godik performed factor analysis based on the 1960 Olympic Games. Most of these studies used a small dataset.

Predicting the final points based on the first day results was not previously studied. The only study that aimed to clarify the performance structure based on the body characteristics of the athletes, Brodani (2006). The aim of this study is to predict the final points based on the results of the first day events. Four predictive models will be used to leverage historical data on decathletes' performances in each of the five events from the first day and develop a mathematical relationship between individual events scores and the overall point totals. We will then compare the accuracy of these models to identify the best model to represent this data.

2. Data

This study includes a dataset gathered over about 40 years (1984 – 2023) of decathlon data for 10 Olympic games and 18 world championships (1984 – 2023). The data were collected starting from 1984 to make the dataset more consistent as a new scoring table was applied in the 1984 Olympic Games. The data were obtained from Olympidia, which is a research site that contains the results

and profiles of all Olympic games and athletes, and informative descriptions for the Games. The variables that were collected are athlete rank, athlete name, country, total points, 100 meters (100m - seconds), Long jump (LJ - meter), Shot put (SP - meter), High jump (HJ - meter), 400 meters (400m - seconds), 110 meters hurdles (110mh - seconds), Discus throw (DT - meter), Pole vault (PV - meter), Javelin throw (JT - meter), 1500 meters (1500m – minutes:seconds), and medals.

The total point score is calculated by adding the points of the ten events. There are three mathematical equations that are used to calculate the points for each group of events: track, jump, and throw.

Two days of high performance in the decathlon is both physically and mentally taxing, so not completing a decathlon is common, and the final points will not count for decathletes that didn't finish more than 1 event, as that results in missing values. Therefore, all rows with missing values were removed from the dataset, which resulted in a dataset with 595 observations.

3. Methodology

The whole dataset was used for the exploratory data analysis (EDA) and multiple linear regression analysis. To achieve the aim of this study, the dataset was split into a training data (90%) and test data (10%). The main model was the ordinary least square regression model (multiple linear regression model), but since the same athlete will compete in 10 different events, a significant correlation between some events were expected, which may cause issues with multicollinearity. Some other regression models were applied for this dataset to handle the multicollinearity issue when present. These models included the principal component regression (PCR) model, partial least squares (PLS) regression model, and quantile regression (QR) model.

The training and test sets were resampled from the original dataset 10,000 times. To take into account the variability between the random samples, the root mean square error (RMSE) for each model was calculated for each resampling iteration to compare the models' performances.

4. Analysis

The data analysis was performed using the R 4.3.1 language. Table 1 presents some important summary statistics that were calculated for each event and the total points.

Table 1: Characteristic of the Decathlon Total Points and Events

Event (Displine)	Unit	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Standard Deviation
100 meters	Second	10.12	12.12	11.00	10.98	0.28
Long Jump	Meter	5.83	8.24	7.28	7.27	0.32
Shot Put	Meter	8.62	17.54	14.46	14.39	1.17
High Jump	Meter	1.70	2.27	2.00	2.00	0.08
400 meters	Second	45.00	54.81	49.00	49.09	1.25
110 meters hurdle	Second	13.46	17.05	14.57	14.63	0.52
Discus Throw	Meter	14.56	54.97	44.29	44.06	4.06
Pole Vault	Meter	2.80	5.70	4.80	4.78	0.33
Javelin Throw	Meter	39.10	79.05	59.98	59.84	6.16
1500 meters	Second	251.8	333.7	276.2	276.9	12.05
Total Points	Point	5339	9045	8118	8086	429.49

The Olympic record for decathlon points is 9018, scored by Damian Warner (Canada) in Tokyo 2021, compared to the world record of 9126 by Kevin Mayer (France) in the Décastar, which is an annual athletics competition that took place in Talence, France 2018.

A histogram was used to describe the distribution of the total points, which is the variable of interest in this study.

Figure 1: The Distribution of Decathlon Total Points

The histogram shows a slightly left skewed distribution, so the Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test the normality assumption, and test showed that the distribution of the total points doesn't follow a normal distribution ($p\text{-value} \approx 0$).

In order to see which events are significantly correlated with the total points, a Spearman's correlation was performed to evaluate the relationships between the total point and each of the ten events since the distribution of the total points doesn't follow a normal distribution.

The range of the absolute correlation coefficients between the total points and the events is 0.24 – 0.69. Long jump tends to have the strongest relationship with the total points ($r = 0.69$) followed by 110 meters hurdles ($r = -0.60$), whereas 1500 meters has the weakest relationship ($r = -0.24$). Figure 2 represents the Spearman correlation coefficient between the total points and each event in ascending order.

Figure 2: The Correlation Coefficients of the Total Points and the Events

A multiple linear regression model was the primary model applied to illustrate a significant relationship between each of the first day events and the total points. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary Results of the Regression Model (Entire Data)

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P-value
Intercept	6600.80	552.86	11.94	< 0.0001
100 meters	-120.85	38.47	-3.14	0.00177
Long Jump	402.19	31.20	12.89	< 0.0001
Shot Put	150.67	6.81	22.13	< 0.0001
High Jump	1346.58	100.75	12.37	< 0.0001
400 meters	-101.25	7.67	-13.20	< 0.0001

The multiple linear regression results show that the first day events explained more than 83% of the observed variability in the final points (adj. $R^2 = 0.832$). The variance inflation factor (VIF) was calculated to detect the multicollinearity among the first day events, and it showed no evidence of multicollinearity among the events (Table 3).

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) (Entire Data)

Event	100 meters	Long Jump	Shot Put	High Jump	400 meters
VIF	2.18	1.93	1.21	1.29	1.76

The four models, MLR model, PCR model with 3 components, PLS regression model, and QR model, were performed and the root mean square error was calculated for each of the 10,000

resamples. Then, the minimum, maximum, and mean of the RMSE for each model were calculated. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparing the Minimum, Mean, and Maximum of the RMSE for Each Model

Model	Min.	Mean	Max.
Linear Regression	132.4	176.7	222.8
Principal Component Regression	138.3	184.9	233.7
Partial Least Square Regression	131.4	177.0	222.5
Quantile Regression	131.5	177.5	225.9

Table 4 shows that the multiple linear regression model, partial least squares regression model, and quantile regression model give similar results. The principal component regression model with 3 components, gives a higher RMSE compared to the other models.

5. Conclusion

40 years (1984 – 2023) of decathlon data from a combination of 28 Olympic games and world championships were used to predict the final points of the decathlon based on the results of the first day events. The first day events were significantly associated with the total points, and the long jump was the most highly correlated event to the total points. The training and test sets were resampled 10,000 times to avoid any variability between the selected samples that may affect the results. The average of the 10,000 RMSE for each of the four models showed that the multiple linear regression model, partial least squares regression model, and quantile regression model provided similar results. Since the multiple linear regression model is the simplest of the four models, we can conclude that it can be used to predict the final results.

6. References

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